

Complete Bell Polynomials and Recurrence Relations for Arithmetic Functions

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Abstract:

We use the Z-transform to solve a type of recurrence relation satisfied by the number of representations of an integer n as the sum of squares and as the sum of triangular numbers, and also by the color partitions of n ; the corresponding solution is in terms of the complete Bell polynomials.

Keywords: *sum of divisors function, Z-transform, sums of squares, color partitions, recurrence relations, sums of triangular numbers, bell polynomials, sum of inverses of odd divisors of an integer.*

Introduction

We know the following recurrence relations (Andrews, Jha & López-Bonilla, 2023; Pathan et al., 2023):

$$n r_k(n) = -2k \sum_{j=1}^n (-1)^j j D(j) r_k(n-j),$$

$$n t_k(n) = -k \sum_{j=1}^n j T(j) t_k(n-j), \quad (1)$$

$$n p_k(n) = -k \sum_{j=1}^n \sigma(j) p_k(n-j),$$

where σ is the sum of divisors function (Apostol, 1976; Hardy & Wright, 1979; Sivaramakrishnan, 1989; Sivaraman & López-Bonilla, 2023); $r_k(n)$ and $t_k(n)$ are the number of representations of n as a sum of k squares and k triangular numbers, respectively (Tausky, 1970; Grosswald, 1984; Grosswald, 1985; Ono et al., 1995; Cooper, 2001; Moreno & Wagstaff, 2006), besides, $p_k(n)$ is the number of color partitions of n (Lazarev et al., 2010; López-Bonilla & Yaljí Montiel-Pérez, 2021; López-Bonilla & Morales-García, 2022; López-Bonilla et al. 2021); finally, in (1) we have the expressions:

$$D(j) = \sum_{\text{odd } d|j} \frac{1}{d}, \quad T(j) = \sum_{d|j} \frac{1+2(-1)^d}{d} = \frac{1}{j} \sum_{d|j} (-1)^d d. \quad (2)$$

Then it is natural to study recurrence relations with the structure of a Cauchy convolution (Sivaramakrishnan, 1989):

$$n f_k(n) = \sum_{j=1}^n h(j) f_k(n-j), \quad k \geq 1, \quad n \geq 0, \quad (3)$$

verifying the properties $f_k(0) = 1 \quad \forall k$ and $h(0) = 0$.

In Sec. 2 we apply the Z- transform to (3) to obtain the following solution (Debnath & Bhatta, 2007; Patra, 2018; López-Bonilla, Vidal-Beltrán & Zúñiga-Segundo, 2018a; Vidal-Beltrán & Zúñiga-Segundo, 2018b; López-Bonilla, López-Vázquez & Vidal-Beltrán, 2018):

$$f_k(n) = \frac{1}{n!} B_n(0! h(1), 1! h(2), 2! h(3), \dots, (n-1)! h(n)), \quad (4)$$

in terms of the complete Bell polynomials (Kölbig, 1994; Johnson, 2002; Connon, 2010; Wikipedia, N/A).

Solution of (3)

If $F(z)$ and $G(z)$ are the Z-transforms of the sequences $\{f_k(0), f_k(1), f_k(2), \dots\}$ and $\{h(0), h(1), \dots\}$, respectively:

$$F(z) = 1 + \frac{f_k(1)}{z} + \frac{f_k(2)}{z^2} + \dots, \quad H(z) = \frac{h(1)}{z} + \frac{h(2)}{z^2} + \dots, \quad (5)$$

then (3) implies the differential equation:

$$-z \frac{d}{dz} F = H(z) F(z), \quad (6)$$

whose integration gives the solution:

$$\ln F = \frac{h(1)}{z} + \frac{h(2)}{2z^2} + \frac{h(3)}{3z^3} + \dots, \quad (7)$$

that is:

$$F(z) := \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} f_k(n) \frac{1}{z^n} = \exp\left(\sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \frac{h(j)}{j} \frac{1}{z^j}\right). \quad (8)$$

On the other hand, we have the generating function of the complete Bell polynomials (Wikipedia, N/A):

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n!} B_n(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) \frac{1}{z^n} = \exp\left(\sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \frac{x_j}{j!} \frac{1}{z^j}\right), \quad (9)$$

whose comparison with (8) implies (4).

This completes the proof.

Application of (4) to $r_k(n)$, $t_k(n)$ and $p_k(n)$.

The result (4) gives the solution of recurrence relations with the structure (3), then its application to (1) allows obtain the following interesting explicit expressions:

$$r_k(n) = \frac{1}{n!} B_n(2k \cdot 1! D(1), -2k \cdot 2! D(2), 2k \cdot 3! D(3), \dots, -2k (-1)^n \cdot n! D(n)),$$

$$t_k(n) = \frac{1}{n!} B_n(-k \cdot 1! T(1), -k \cdot 2! T(2), -k \cdot 3! T(3), \dots, -k \cdot n! T(n)), \quad (10)$$

$$p_k(n) = \frac{1}{n!} B_n(-k \cdot 0! \sigma(1), -k \cdot 1! \sigma(2), -k \cdot 2! \sigma(3), \dots, -k \cdot (n-1)! \sigma(n)).$$

Besides, we know the recurrence relation (Osler, 2007; Flajolet & Sedgewick, 2008):

$$n p(n) = \sum_{j=1}^n \sigma(j) p(n-j), \quad (11)$$

for the partition function (Apostol, 1976; Hardy & Wright, 1979; Sivaramakrishnan, 1989), hence from (4):

$$p(n) = \frac{1}{n!} B_n(0! \sigma(1), 1! \sigma(2), 2! \sigma(3), \dots, (n-1)! \sigma(n)). \quad (12)$$

As a last application, Robbins deduced the following recurrence (Robbins, 1999; Robbins, 2002):

$$n p_D(n) = \sum_{j=1}^n \sigma_0(j) p_D(n-j), \sigma_0(n) = \sum_{\text{odd } d|n} d = \sum_{d|n} (-1)^{d-1} \frac{n}{d}, \quad (13)$$

where $p_D(n)$ is the number of partitions of n using only distinct parts, therefore:

$$p_D(n) = \frac{1}{n!} B_n(0! \sigma_0(1), 1! \sigma_0(2), 2! \sigma_0(3), \dots, (n-1)! \sigma_0(n)). \quad (14)$$

Conclusion

In this short paper, we have obtained nice expressions for obtaining number of representations of a positive integer n in terms of k triangular numbers and k square numbers. We have also obtained a nice expression for

expressing color partitions of a positive integer n in terms of complete Bell polynomials. We have used Cauchy convolution and Z - transform technique in order to obtain such expressions.

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